

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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ENHANCING TEAMWORK AND IMPROVING COMMUNICATION
ON SURGICAL UNITS USING TEAMSTEPS[®]

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Teamwork and communication are important factors in reducing medical errors and improving job satisfaction (Chachula, Myrick, & Yonge, 2015; Miller, Kim, Silverman, & Bauer, 2018; World Health Organization [WHO], 2011). The Agency of Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) and the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) collaborated to create Team Strategies and Tools to Enhance Performance and Patient Safety (TeamSTEPPS), an evidence-based program to improve communication and collaboration among providers (AHRQ, 2013). The purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project was to improve (a) teamwork, (b) communication, and (c) job satisfaction among surgical staff through the implementation of TeamSTEPPS in a 162-bed acute care community hospital in an urban area of Southern California.

The settings for the QI project were three surgical units: (a) Same Day Surgery, (b) the Operating Room, and (c) Post Anesthesia Care Unit. The QI team implemented a four-hour TeamSTEPPS training session consisting of (a) PowerPoint lecture, (b) group activities, and (c) role-playing. Two surveys, the Brief TeamSTEPPS Teamwork Perceptions Questionnaire (T-TPQ) and the Healthcare Environment Survey Job Satisfaction Subscale (JSS), were administered before the training and one month after. Responses on individual survey items were dichotomized to two variables with *agree* and *strongly agree* being one variable versus all other responses. A percent change from baseline response to follow-up response was calculated to examine the influence of

TeamSTEPPS training on job satisfaction and perceptions of teamwork and communication.

Seventeen participants completed the pre- and post-surveys. The three items on the JSS that demonstrated the most improvement were (a) *satisfaction with teamwork* (36.4% pre, 58.8% post, increased 61% from baseline); (b) *satisfaction with organizational reward* (13.6% pre, 29.4% post, increased 116% from baseline); and (c) *satisfaction with physician respect* (28.6% pre, 52.9% post, increased 85% from baseline). The three items on the Brief Team T-TPQ that demonstrated marked improvements were (a) *the supervisor taking time to create a plan of care with staff* (45.5% pre, 68.8% post, increased 51.2% from baseline); (b) *the supervisor considers staff input about patient care* (40.9% pre, 62.5% post, increased 52.8% from baseline); and (c) *staff assist colleagues during high workloads* (59.1% pre, 94.1% post, increased 59.2% from baseline). One item on the JSS showed a marked decrease, *satisfaction with opportunities for growth and development* (40.9% pre, 29.4% post, a 28.1% decrease from baseline).

The findings generally demonstrated marked improvements in teamwork, communication, and job satisfaction among surgical staff at the facility because of TeamSTEPPS implementation. However, the item from the JSS that demonstrated a large decrement warrants attention from hospital administrators and clinical directors. This QI project adds to the literature by confirming the results found by other researchers and provides evidence of the positive effects and challenges to implementing TeamSTEPPS in community-based, acute settings.

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INTRODUCTION

The Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations (JCAHO) published its 2018 National Patient Safety Goals (NPSGs), which identified communication as a priority focus for quality improvement. One third of the 2018 NPSGs pertain to the content and timeliness of communication between healthcare providers (Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations [JCAHO], 2018). Early work in this field that included root cause analyses of sentinel events identified communication failures as a leading cause of errors (JCAHO, 2004). Furthermore, approximately 75% of those sentinel events led to patient demise. In 2013, JCAHO determined communication now had become the second most common cause of sentinel events (Beckers Hospital Review, 2013). Communication failures still accounted for 65 percent of sentinel events. It is vital that healthcare workers improve their communication skills in order to optimize nursing care and patient outcomes.

Teamwork, like communication, is an important factor in reducing medical errors and improving job satisfaction (Chachula, Myrick, & Yonge, 2015; Miller, Kim, Silverman, & Bauer, 2018; World Health Organization [WHO], 2011). Moreover, nurses who reported positive work relationships and higher levels of group cohesion also reported higher rates of job satisfaction (Tourangeau & Cranley, 2006). Not surprisingly, nurses who reported higher levels of job satisfaction have been more likely to remain at their current employment setting and less likely to leave the nursing profession (Kalisch, Lee, & Rochman, 2010). Nursing satisfaction is an essential topic as the U.S. nursing supply will be short of approximately 110,000 nurses by 2020 (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2018).

Significance of the Problem

The cost of poor communication, lack of teamwork, low job satisfaction, and high nurse turnover affect patient safety and are concerns for healthcare organizations (Chachula et al., 2015; Vessey, DeMarco, & DiFazio, 2010). The seminal Institute of Medicine report, "To Err is Human" (1999) estimated the costs of preventable medical errors at \$17-19 billion and linked these errors to 98,000 deaths per year. However, subsequent studies have stated that actually more than 98,000 individuals die yearly due to errors (Makary & Daniel, 2016). HealthGrades (2004) calculated that there are approximately 195,000 deaths annually due to errors among hospitalized Medicare patients. John Hopkins patient safety experts have suggested 250,000 deaths occur per year due to medical errors, making medical errors the third leading cause of death in the United States (Makary & Daniel, 2016).

Poor communication and a lack of teamwork not only compromise patient safety, they contribute significantly to burnout (Chachula et al., 2015; Vessey et al., 2010). Researchers have estimated the cost of nurse turnover to be \$80,000 per nurse (Moran et al., 2017). Not only has it been costly for healthcare organizations to retrain new employees after nurses leave, healthcare workers have been more likely to commit errors in hospitals with higher turnover rates (Duffield, Roche, Dimitrelis, & Homer, 2014). At the author's hospital, communication, and teamwork may be less than optimal. In a recent hospital wide survey, 56 percent of the nursing staff from the project hospital reported important patient care information was lost during shift changes and only 43 percent reported satisfaction in working with staff from other units.

In 2006, AHRQ and the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) collaborated to create Team Strategies and Tools to Enhance Performance and Patient Safety (TeamSTEPPS[®]), an evidence-based program to improve communication and collaboration among providers (AHRQ, 2013). The AHRQ website has educational materials readily available as well as evaluation tools for improving communication and teamwork across a variety of settings.

Purpose of the Project

The purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project was to improve teamwork and communication among surgical staff through the implementation of TeamSTEPPS in a community hospital in an urban area of Southern California.

Theoretical Framework and Model

According to Bonnel and Smith (2014), theories and frameworks provide a foundation for the development, implementation, and evaluation of clinical projects. Theory-guided practice is important to achieve alignment between processes and products in the healthcare field (Zaccagnini & White, 2017). In addition, a model is necessary to demonstrate how components of the project are interrelated. This QI project integrated both the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DIT) theory and the TeamSTEPPS training model to enhance teamwork and improve communication among surgical staff.

The TeamSTEPPS Framework

TeamSTEPPS is a public training curriculum to produce highly effective healthcare teams (AHRQ, 2013). Researchers have used the TeamSTEPPS approach to improve outcomes such as (a) staff satisfaction, (b) staff and patient perceptions of staff teamwork, (c) staff perception of leadership, (d) staff communication skills, and (e)

cultures of safety (Castner, Foltz-Ramos, Schwartz, & Ceravolo, 2012; Gaston, Short, Ralyea, & Casterline, 2016; Nippita et al., 2017; Vertino, 2014). The TeamSTEPPS training program is adaptable to various clinical settings and incorporates five key constructs: (a) team structure, (b) leadership, (c) communication, (d) situation monitoring, and (e) mutual support (AHRQ, 2013).

TeamSTEPPS provides definitions for each of the competencies with team structure reflecting the four team-based competencies of (a) leadership, (b) communication, (c) situation monitoring, and (d) mutual support. The AHRQ has defined leadership as the ability to motivate staff and provide them with the resources needed to optimally work towards shared goals. Situation monitoring is having an understanding of what others on the healthcare team do and monitoring other teammate's performances (AHRQ, 2013). Mutual support is anticipating if another team member has needs and providing feedback when necessary. Communication is the ability to exchange information with other members of the healthcare team employing structured communication techniques (AHRQ, 2013). This QI project included training sessions that covered all four team-based competencies, but focused more heavily on communication.

The TeamSTEPPS figure has multiple two-way arrows to demonstrate how the four team-based constructs are interrelated to each other and to the (a) knowledge, (b) attitudes, and (c) performance of team outcomes (See Figure 1; AHRQ, 2013). Members of the healthcare team should have the knowledge of a shared mental model. Furthermore, their attitudes should display mutual trust and be team-oriented (AHRQ, 2013). Lastly, their performance should be adaptable, accurate, productive, efficient, and safe. By focusing on staff knowledge, skills, and performance related to the four team-

based competencies, TeamSTEPPS training helps to change the culture of an organization to improve team performance and create safer practices (AHRQ, 2011).

Figure 1. The TeamSTEPPS framework. From “TeamSTEPPS Guide to Action: Creating a Safety Net for Your Healthcare Organization” by AHRQ, 2011, p. 12.

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DIT)

Facilitating the adoption of TeamSTEPPS includes consideration of how to leverage staff attributes to optimize acceptance and sustainability of the TeamSTEPPS concepts. The diffusion of innovation theory (DIT) provides a theoretical framework for leveraging the attributes of staff to improve adoption of a new practice. According to Rogers (2003), the key concepts of the DIT include (a) the innovation, (b) communication channels, (c) time, and (d) the social system. An innovation can be a new idea, behavior, or product for a particular group. Communication channels are how

messages get from one person to another (Rogers, 2003). In the DIT, time is a component in relation to the rate of adoption of the innovation. A social system is a set of interconnected units (people) that engage due to a shared problem and common goal (Rogers, 2003).

Rogers (2003) proposed that populations considering innovations present as five unequal subgroups according to their propensity to accept an innovation (see Figure 2). The first individuals to adopt were the *innovators*. Innovators were imaginative visionaries who sought new ideas, behaviors, and products (Rogers, 2003). The next group of individuals was the *early adopters* who joined in because the benefits of the innovation become evident. The *later adopters*, made of the *early* and *late majority*, were the next subgroup who adopted because the innovation had already become mainstream (Rogers, 2003). The *laggards* were the last to adopt, only after exerting resistance by criticizing why the innovation will not work.

Figure 2. Diffusion of innovation theory: The five subgroups. Adapted by John Hopkins Center for Communication Programs from the “*Diffusion of Innovations*” by Rogers, E. M., 2003, Free Press Publishing.

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory and TeamSTEPPS

In implementing TeamSTEPPS (the innovation) at the practice site, it was important to be mindful of the positives and negatives of each subgroup. The innovators in this QI project were the nursing director and charge nurses. They had to lead by example, as their support for the innovation was vital to its success among the staff. The early adopters tended to be staff with less experience and who were more receptive to new practices because they were still developing their work habits (Olson-Sitki, Kirkbride, & Forbes, 2015). New graduate nurses tended to be flexible as their education emphasized evidence-based practice in a dynamic healthcare system. The late adopters may have been the more seasoned nurses whereas the laggards may have been the veteran nurses who had developed habits they believed had worked for them for a long time and they resisted adopting new practices (Olson-Sitki et al., 2015).

Decisions to adopt may be influenced by (a) an innovation's simplicity, (b) relative advantage, and (c) compatibility with the organization's culture and norms. Approaches to encourage diffusion could include (a) legitimization by personnel of high status, (b) establishment of change agents to interact with the adopters, and (c) advocacy by the organization (Dearing, 2009). For instance, if a charge nurse accepts an innovation, it is highly likely that a new graduate registered nurse will adopt as well. Other attributes of an innovation, such as (a) observability, (b) trialability, and (c) visibility, can affect its adoptability; other authors have even added (a) perceived liability, (b) risk, (c) status, and (d) uncertainty (Dearing, 2009). *Observability* was the degree to which results of an innovation are observable to others. Observability was important in this QI project because the staff needed to see the tangible outcomes from the adoption of

the innovation prior to implementing it in their own practice. Moreover, *trialability* was the degree to which an innovation can be experimented with on a limited basis, and *visibility* was the degree to which the utility of the innovation was apparent within an organization (Rogers, 2003).

Speeding the rate of adoption could encourage late adopters to become early adopters. One method to accelerate the adoption of the TeamSTEPPS communication and teamwork tools was to establish unit champions who encouraged staff and served as resources to the staff (Dearing, 2009). This was essential to gain buy-in from the healthcare care providers. Additionally, the implementation team displayed TeamSTEPPS posters on the units to demonstrate advocacy by the organization and serve as a reminder for staff to utilize the skills they practiced during the educational sessions.

The TeamSTEPPS model and the DIT worked synergistically in this project to facilitate adoption of new behaviors related to teamwork and communication among surgical staff in an acute care setting. The theory and model provided unique contributions to the QI project and guided the author in identifying ways to apply a systematic approach toward initiating a practice change in a community hospital setting.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to examine the role of TeamSTEPPS in improving teamwork and communication within the hospital setting. A literature review provides the foundation for an evidence-based synthesis of existing knowledge (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). The library databases searched included (a) EBSCO, (B) PubMed, (c) CINAHL, (d) Cochrane Library, and (e) the AHRQ database. Key terms searched were TeamSTEPPS, communication, teamwork, and nursing satisfaction. The limits applied to this literature search were articles that were: (a) peer reviewed, (b) published from 2013 to 2019, and (c) published in English. The literature review was not limited to articles published in the United States. Exclusions were based on relevance to the project topics. Lastly, additional sources reviewed included Google scholar and the Institute for Healthcare Improvement website.

Teamwork

Teamwork, also known as collaboration or group cohesion in the literature, is vital to creating a patient safety culture (Vertino, 2014; Wong, Gang, Szyld, & Mahoney, 2016). High-functioning teams make fewer errors, leading to safer patient care conditions. On the contrary, poor teamwork causes communication failures, heavier individual workloads, and decreased nurse satisfaction (Kalisch et al., 2010; Welp & Manser, 2016). Within the last two decades, there has been a major focus on borrowing strategies from aviation, military, and other high-reliability industries to improve teamwork within healthcare agencies (Gaston et al., 2016). High reliability organizations have operated in complex, high-risk circumstances for extended periods of time without serious accidents by prioritizing safety over all other performance measures (Patient

Safety Network, 2017). Healthcare environments are also high-stress and high-stakes settings, so it is clear why the AHRQ and the DoD collaborated to create TeamSTEPPS training for healthcare providers (AHRQ, 2011).

TeamSTEPPS training has been shown to improve healthcare providers' perception of teamwork and communication in various acute care settings (Gaston et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2017; Lisbon et al., 2016; Vertino, 2014). Multiple researchers have reported on the effectiveness of TeamSTEPPS training (See Appendix A, Table 2). The largest study to date involved 306 multidisciplinary participants who underwent a four-hour training session with pre and post intervention assessments (Brock et al., 2013). The study participants improved in the constructs of (a) patients advocacy ($p < 0.001$), (b) motivation ($p < 0.001$), (c) self-efficacy ($p = 0.005$), and (d) team communication ($p < 0.001$). In addition, Vertino (2014) implemented TeamSTEPPS among nursing staff in an acute care hospital and found significant improvement across all five TeamSTEPPS constructs (team structure, leadership, communication, situational monitoring, and mutual support; $p \leq .001$ for all areas). Results from the study by Gaston et al. (2016) revealed that staff openness to communication and teamwork increased by 21% and 17%, respectively, on the Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture (HSOPSC; $p < 0.05$). This author implemented TeamSTEPPS hoping to achieve similar outcomes in teamwork and communication among the nursing staff at the project facility.

Measures of communication may provide different outcomes, even within a single study. For example, Wong et al. (2016) found significant improvements on all TeamSTEPPS constructs except communication on the TeamSTEPPS Teamwork Attitude Questionnaire (T-TAQ) among staff. Wong et al. (2016) also found significant

improvements in responses to three questions related to communication on the HSOPSC. The three questions referred to (a) frequency of error and near miss reporting ($p = 0.028$), (b) teamwork in hospital units ($p = 0.035$), and (c) handoff and transition of care reporting ($p = 0.024$). A safe patient care culture allows staff to feel comfortable reporting errors. Okafor et al. found an increase in the frequency of error and near miss reporting that can be attributed to improved communication and teamwork among staff as medical errors are often underreported (2015). However, communication is a skill that requires time to build confidence in performing effectively. One might argue that the HSOPSC result was a more valid measure because it was administered a year after the training, whereas Wong and colleagues administered the T-TAQ immediately following their training session. Therefore, administering the HSOPSC after one year allowed for the measurement of a practice effect. To determine a more long-term practice effect, this author implemented evaluation measures one month after the training session to measure the sustainability of the project outcomes.

It is important to promote long-term adoption of an innovation through maintenance interventions. Vertino (2014) provided mentoring and coaching after TeamSTEPPS training to sustain the improvements of teamwork and communication behaviors among staff. The researchers in this study suggested a need to evaluate TeamSTEPPS outcomes with and without mentoring and coaching. In another study, Lee et al. (2017) sought to sustain TeamSTEPPS principles by implementing a bundle of activities focusing on leadership and communication. The bundle included: (a) a lecture with videos on leadership, (b) an online self-paced module on communication, (c) an emailed one-page summary on leadership skills, and (d) one hour of leadership grand

rounds. The bundle had the greatest influence on sustaining leadership skills, such as (a) being assertive, (b) providing directions, and (c) supporting other team members (Lee et al., 2017). The staff demonstrated the next most significant improvements in the area of communication behaviors, specifically in the quantity and quality of the information shared among team members. Although reinforcement techniques were not feasible for the timeline of this QI project, the author supplemented with (a) mentoring, (b) coaching, (c) email reminders, and (d) knowledge checks at staff meetings after the TeamSTEPPS training to improve sustainability.

Communication

Effective communication is the exchange of clear, brief, complete, and timely information and includes the opportunity to ask questions and clarify any ambiguities (Lee et al., 2017). Deficits in communication occur when critical information is not communicated between team members or when there is a lack of understanding about each member's roles and responsibilities (Vermeir et al., 2017). In addition, use of varying terminology can also lead to miscommunications. D'agostino et al. (2017) conducted focus groups to identify factors that inhibited staff from communicating safety concerns ("speaking up"). The researchers identified six themes: (a) staff rapport and personality, (b) perceived competence and efficacy of speaking up, (c) role relations and hierarchy, (d) fear of retaliation, (e) institutional regulations, and (f) time pressure. Self-efficacy in communicating patient safety concerns increased after TeamSTEPPS training ($p = 0.009$; D'agostino et al., 2017). Although this study's participants were more likely to stop and ask for clarity, they were less likely to minimize the hierarchy, a common communication barrier at non-academic hospitals.

Communication can be facilitated through a variety of standardized tools. TeamSTEPPS has endorsed the use of the situation, background, assessment, and recommendation (SBAR) tool for reporting a transition of care (TOC) or a critical result (AHRQ, 2017). The U.S. Navy first developed the SBAR format to improve reporting of critical information (Eberhardt, 2014). This tool has been an efficient method to organize information. Achrekar et al. (2016) performed audits on nurses' compliance with using SBAR before and after formal education on this approach. They found a significant improvement in compliance, specifically in the situation portion of the reporting tool ($p = 0.043$). Although it has been known that teamwork and communication have been key to delivering safe, quality care to patients, providers frequently have lacked formal training in these areas (Leonard, Graham, & Bonacum, 2004). The Achrekar et al. (2016) project employed formalized training in SBAR to improve standardized communication and teamwork at the project hospital.

Poor teamwork and team communication contributes to (a) low morale, (b) decreased nurse job satisfaction, and (c) increased nurse turnover (Kalisch et al., 2010; Vertino, 2014; Welp & Manser, 2016). Kalisch et al. (2010) conducted a cross-sectional study of 3,675 nurses and found that interactions with patients, colleagues, and managers were an important extrinsic source of job satisfaction ($p < 0.001$). The researchers used the Nursing Teamwork Survey, which was based on a teamwork theory that emphasized teamwork behaviors consistent with the TeamSTEPPS model. Nursing staff who were not satisfied with their jobs contributed to high turnover rates within healthcare organizations and displayed lower levels of productivity. This study appears to support what has been witnessed at the project hospital - a lack of the sense of teamwork and job

satisfaction among nursing staff, causing the organization to have high turnover rates. Thus, the author implemented TeamSTEPPS to improve teamwork and communication among staff, improve job satisfaction, and decrease turnover rates at the project hospital.

TeamSTEPPS Implementation Strategies

The literature contained a number of studies using a variety of methodologies for implementing and evaluating TeamSTEPPS training. Although there was an abundance of evidence supporting the efficacy of TeamSTEPPS training on perceptions of teamwork, the majority of studies employed non-experimental designs (D'agostino et al., 2017; Gaston et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2017; Lisbon et al., 2016; Vertino, 2014). However, several TeamSTEPPS researchers conducted mixed methods studies, which strengthen the body of evidence (D'agostino et al., 2017; Gaston et al., 2016; Natafghi et al., 2017; Wong et al., 2016). Another weakness witnessed in many of the studies of TeamSTEPPS was small sample sizes. As noted by Kim (2014), future researchers may wish to consider (a) conducting training with larger samples, (b) implementing more rigorous educational interventions and research methods, and (c) assessing sustainable effects of TeamSTEPPS over an extended period time.

On the other hand, some studies utilized only qualitative methods (Oldland, Currey, Considine, & Allen, 2017; Ward, Zhu, Lampman, & Stewart, 2015). Using an exploratory descriptive approach, Oldland et al. (2017) found improved communication after a team-based learning intervention. The nurses in this study reported a need to speak more concisely so that others could understand them better. By conducting semi-structured interviews after TeamSTEPPS training, Ward et al. (2015) identified ways to improve the TeamSTEPPS implementation process such as using active learning

activities during training and developing action plans for follow up with staff. A review of qualitative TeamSTEPPS studies suggested valuable information to consider while implementing and evaluating the training program in the setting of the DNP project.

Clinical Outcomes of TeamSTEPPS Training

There is a paucity of literature examining the effects of TeamSTEPPS on patients' clinical outcomes. For example, Libson et al. (2016) and Vertino et al. (2014) examined changes in knowledge and attitudes. Unfortunately, they also stated that it was beyond the scope of their pilot studies to evaluate patient and quality outcomes. Another study examined incident reporting and found no improvements following TeamSTEPPS training (Gaston et al., 2016). One limitation of incident reporting as an outcome is that incidents are self-reported and therefore tend to be underreported. A few studies reported patient outcomes including decreased rates of nosocomial infections and pressure ulcers as well as improved patient pain satisfaction scores after implementing TeamSTEPPS (Gibbons, 2015; Kim, 2014; Mayer et al., 2011). However, there were weaknesses noted in two of these studies. Kim (2014) did not find statistical significance in her results and Gibbons (2015) did not report a *p* value for significance.

To strengthen the evidence of TeamSTEPPS on nursing outcomes and to address the concerns of the project site, the author evaluated job satisfaction in the month following implementation of the TeamSTEPPS training. While these outcomes have not previously been studied after TeamSTEPPS implementation, the literature demonstrated positive results in job satisfaction as a result of improved teamwork and communication with fellow coworkers ($p < 0.001$; Kalisch et al., 2010; Vermeir et al., 2017).

Barriers to Implementation of TeamSTEPPS

In addition to limited clinical outcomes, there were also barriers noted in the literature related to TeamSTEPPS implementation. Barriers included (a) lack of administrative support and resources, (b) minimal to no physician involvement, and (c) resistance to change by veteran staff (Natafqi et al., 2017; Ward et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2016). The theory that the author selected for this QI project was the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT), which has aimed to describe how innovations were adopted within a population (Rogers, 2003). The DIT has suggested that face-to-face communication was more powerful than mass media (Robinson, 2009). Consistent with DIT, hospitals that successfully implemented TeamSTEPPS had administrators who were visible to their staff (Natafqi et al., 2017). The author considered how to help laggards, such as the veteran staff, to see other laggards successfully adopt TeamSTEPPS practices in order to optimize TeamSTEPPS adoption into work processes (Robinson, 2009).

Most reports related to TeamSTEPPS took place at large academic hospitals (D'agostino et al., 2017; Gaston et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2017; Lisbon et al., 2016; Vertino, 2014; Ward et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2016). Small community hospitals, such as the project hospital, have had fewer personnel and resources (Lee et al., 2017; Ward et al., 2015). However, the culture at the project hospital has been that the staff is a “family” as the staff members rely on each other more frequently due to having less personnel and resources. Ward et al. (2015) were the only researchers to report about TeamSTEPPS implementation within a community hospital. However, they used a qualitative approach to evaluate their compliance with best practices for implementing TeamSTEPPS. Ward et al. (2015) found that the educators provided feedback during the TeamSTEPPS training

at only two hospitals (13%). The implementation team at the project hospital included feedback as part of the teaching plan to increase adoption among the staff.

Conclusion

Overall, the quality of the evidence was moderate as studies supported improvement in perceptions and behaviors related to teamwork and communication that resulted from TeamSTEPPS training. However, there were limited studies that reported on patient or nursing outcomes, with most studies reporting small sample sizes. The literature was also fragmented, as researchers who implemented TeamSTEPPS utilized diverse outcome measures. Researchers in the literature adapted the TeamSTEPPS curriculum to implement its principles in various clinical settings including many surgical and emergency departments (AHRQ, 2013; Gaston et al., 2016; Vertino, 2014). The results of this QI project added to the literature by demonstrating TeamSTEPPS usefulness in improving teamwork and communication, leading to increased staff satisfaction.

METHODS

The author developed a detailed plan to implement and evaluate TeamSTEPPS training for surgical staff at the project hospital. This section describes the (a) setting and sample, (b) ethical considerations, (c) measures, (d) procedures, and (e) data analysis for this QI project.

Design

A quality improvement (QI) approach was used to improve perceptions of (a) teamwork, (b) communication, and (c) job satisfaction on surgical units in a community hospital through the implementation of TeamSTEPPS.

Setting/Sample

The author implemented this QI project at a 162-bed acute care, non-academic community hospital in Southern California. All staff members (registered nurses [RNs], techs, orderlies, and coordinators) from the surgical units employed at the project hospital from September 2018 to October 2018 were included in the TeamSTEPPS training. Surgical units at the project facility included the operating room (OR), recovery or post-anesthesia care unit (PACU), and same day surgery (SDS). The nursing director and charge nurse of these units announced details related to the training during their staff meetings and shift huddles. Furthermore, the hospital educators created flyers posted near the time clocks and in the staff lounge. The training course involved 24 staff members. The chief executive officer made the decision to educate the surgical unit nursing staff because of their high turnover rates and the exclusivity of these units. In addition, these units have a high interaction rate as patients move through all three units in a single day. Therefore, implementing an effective teamwork and communication training program at

this location was likely to have the largest influence on staff and patient outcomes.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to implementing this QI project, the author considered potential ethical concerns. No patient data were accessed for this project. All data that pertained to the staff were de-identified. The project author removed participant names once a numeric code was assigned.

There were some concerns about staff well since they went through the TeamSTEPPS training role-playing. Although role-playing is an effective learning activity, it can be very stressful for participants (Cantrell, Meyer, & Mosack, 2017). Nursing students from a mixed-methods study shared that they felt high levels of anxiety when performing in simulations, which is similar to role-playing. In this study, researchers operationalized anxiety using cortisol levels, which were three times greater than baseline after participating in simulation exercises (Jones et al., 2011). In order to mitigate the potential for negative consequences related to staff engaging in role-playing, the facilitator provided encouragement to the participants and allowed sufficient time to read the scenarios and prepare accordingly. Additionally, the educator informed the staff their performance in role-playing would not affect their employment status.

The author obtained an institutional permission letter from the designated administrator at the hospital to (a) implement the project, (b) access staff members, and (c) use hospital resources for the training. The project was reviewed by the California State University, Long Beach, Institutional Research Board (IRB) and approved as a quality improvement project. To avoid coercion, the project leader informed staff that participation in the project surveys was completely voluntary (completion of the pre/post

DNP surveys) even though the participation in the training was mandatory for their employment. The nurse educators did not need to obtain informed consent from staff members because the IRB deemed this project “non-research.” Lastly, the author offered \$5 gift cards for coffee to incentivize the one-month follow up surveys.

Measures

The author collected demographic information from participants using a brief survey. The survey asked participants to indicate their (a) job role, (b) years of experience at the project facility, (c) education level, and (d) base work unit. The years of experience response options were listed as ranges whereas all other responses were single options. Following the collection of demographic data, the author gathered information to evaluate the effectiveness of the TeamSTEPPS training program.

The Brief TeamSTEPPS Teamwork Perceptions Questionnaire (T-TPQ) has five subscales consistent with the TeamSTEPPS constructs: (a) team structure, (b) communication, (c) situation monitoring, (d) leadership, and (e) mutual support (Castner, Ceravolo, Foltz-Ramos, & Wu, 2013). The 20 items were scored by a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, with 1 representing *strongly disagree* and 5 representing *strongly agree* (See Appendix B). One of the statements from the Brief T-TPQ read: “Staff exchange relevant information as it becomes available.” In a sample of 456 nurses, the Brief T-TPQ subscales demonstrated strong internal consistency between 0.83-0.94 (AHRQ, 2017; Castner, 2012). Furthermore, the survey has demonstrated discriminant validity with self-esteem and control over practice (Castner, 2012). Discriminant validity refers to the test’s ability to measure a specific construct such as the five TeamSTEPPS constructs (Polit & Beck, 2017).

The Healthcare Environment Survey consists of 13 subscales but only questions from the job satisfaction subscale (JSS) were used for the purposes of this QI project (See Appendix C). The composite JSS has 11 questions and has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.93 (J. Nelson, personal communication, May 3, 2018). Items were scored on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 for *strongly disagree* to 7 for *strongly agree*. Example questions included, "I am satisfied with how well nurses and staff in my unit/department work together as a team," and "I am satisfied with the availability of equipment needed to do my job." Dr. John Nelson, the creator of the Healthcare Environment Survey, granted the project leader permission via email to utilize the JSS. The T-TPQ is publicly available on the AHRQ website and AHRQ has encouraged its use in TeamSTEPPS training and research (AHRQ, 2017).

Procedures

Each staff member received a folder as participants filled the surveys using pencil and paper. At the beginning of the training session, the staff members who agreed to participate in the quality improvement project completed (a) the demographic questions, (b) the Brief T-TPQ, and (c) the JSS. All who attended the training received copies of the PowerPoint presentation. On the left side of folder, they received a copy of the Brief T-TPQ and the JSS with instructions to be filled out one month after the training session.

Team Strategies and Tools to Enhance Performance and Patient Safety (TeamSTEPPS®) includes ready-to-use materials and a training curriculum (AHRQ, 2013). The author minimally adapted the TeamSTEPPS curriculum to provide a four-hour training session. The class focused heavily on communication while still including content on leadership, mutual support, and situational monitoring. The class consisted of

a one-hour PowerPoint presentation and then the staff engaged in three hours of role-play and interactive class activities to allow for deeper learning.

An initial step in the training was to increase the staff knowledge of medical errors that are due to communication failures and poor teamwork in healthcare settings. The next step was to persuade the staff to engage in learning the TeamSTEPPS tools by sharing a story about a patient safety issue that occurred within the hospital. Once motivated to learn, the staff decided to learn and implement the skills in patient scenarios presented in the TeamSTEPPS training session.

Communication strategies, such as (a) briefings, (b) team huddle, (c) the two-challenge rule, (d) SBAR, and (e) check-back (AHRQ, 2013), were covered in the class. For example, the two-challenge rule communication strategy refers to a staff member's duty to voice his or her concern at least two times when an initial assertive statement is ignored. Examples of assertive statements include, "I am concerned!" or "This is a safety issue!" (AHRQ, 2013). It was important to focus the classes toward what the staff can realistically implement into their practice to produce better safety outcomes.

Initially, the project leader was going to administer the post Brief T-TPQ immediately after the training, but TeamSTEPPS experts at the master training course discouraged against collecting data and expecting to see a change that quickly. After the training was over, the educator reiterated the instructions to complete and submit the surveys in one month after the training. There were designated folders to submit the surveys anonymously at the one-month post-training mark. Confirmation occurred when the staff worked through case studies and performed in role-playing. The staff members filled out a questionnaire about their perceived self-improvements in communication and

teamwork skills. Extra copies of the surveys were provided one month after if the original copies from the training session were misplaced.

Data Analysis

International Business Machine (IBM) Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS™) Version 25.0 and EXCEL (Microsoft) were used for statistical analysis. Measures of central tendency described the demographic characteristics of the nurses. To ease interpretation of the results and application to clinical practice, responses on individual items were dichotomized to two variables with *agree* and *strongly agree* being one variable versus all other responses. This analytic approach is consistent with current value-based performance measurements (Spekle & Verbeeten, 2014) and other research approaches (Casarett et al., 2010; Kutney-Lee, Brennan, Meterko, & Ersek, 2015; Kutney-Lee et al., 2015). A percent change from baseline response to follow-up response was calculated to examine the influence of TeamSTEPPS training on job satisfaction and perceptions of teamwork and communication.

Conclusion

This section detailed (a) the procedures for this QI project, (b) the project setting, (c) a sample description, (d) the steps for implementation and evaluation, and (e) the relevant ethical considerations related to the project. The author provided a project timeline, which included IRB submission and approval. Once approved by the Doctor of Nursing Practice Faculty Team Lead and committee chair members and the IRB, the author began the implementation of this QI project in September 2018. The author reported any necessary adjustments in the implementation plan to the IRB in a prompt manner.

RESULTS

Of the 24 surgical staff members who attended the TeamSTEPPS training session, 22 completed the baseline surveys. Seventeen participants (74%) submitted the one-month follow-up surveys. Response rate varied by unit (OR – 50%, PACU – 100%, and SDS – 100%). The sample consisted of (a) predominantly registered nurses (RNs) (72.7%), (b) who worked in the OR (50%), (c) who were baccalaureate educated (50%), and (d) had more than 10 years of experience at the project facility (77.3%; See Table 1).

Table 1

Sample Demographics at Baseline

	<i>N</i>	Percent of Sample
Job Title		
Registered Nurse	16	72.7%
Tech	1	4.5%
Other	5	22.7%
Unit		
Same Day Surgery	3	13.6%
Operating Room	11	50%
Post Anesthesia Care Unit	8	36.4%
Education		
High School Diploma	3	13.6%
Associate Degree	6	27.3%
Bachelor's Degree	11	50%
Master's Degree	0	0%
Years Worked at Project Facility		
Less Than 1 Year	1	4.5%
One to Three Years	1	4.5%
Three to Five Years	3	13.6%
Five to 10 Years	17	77.3%

Note. *N* = Number.

The three items on the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) that demonstrated the most improvement were (a) *satisfaction with teamwork* (36.4% pre, 58.8% post, increased 61% from baseline); (b) *satisfaction with organizational reward* (13.6% pre, 29.4% post, increased 116% from baseline); and (c) *satisfaction with physician respect* (28.6% pre, 52.9% post, increased 85% from baseline; see Figure 3). There were three items on the Brief TeamSTEPPS Teamwork Perceptions Questionnaire (T-TPQ) that demonstrated marked improvements (>50% improvement from baseline; see Figures 4 and 5). These items were: (a) *The supervisor taking time to create a plan of care with staff* (45.5% pre, 68.8% post, increased 51.2% from baseline); (b) *The supervisor considers staff input about patient care* (40.9% pre, 62.5% post, increased 52.8% from baseline); and (c) *Staff assist colleagues during high workloads* (59.1% pre, 94.1% post, increased 59.2% from baseline). Several additional items increased from approximately 10% to 30% over baseline. See Appendix E, Table 4, for examples.

In contrast, three items on the JSS decreased from baseline (one item markedly; See Appendix D, Table 3). These items included (a) *satisfaction with how my manager responds to questions about my work*; (b) *satisfaction with the level of respect for the administration by staff*; and (c) *satisfaction with opportunities for growth and development*. Only one item decreased from baseline on the Brief T-TPQ, *Staff understand their roles and responsibilities* (90.5% pre, 82.4% post, 8.9% decrement). On the Brief T-TPQ, the two questions that showed the least amount of improvement were *staff verbally verify information received* and *the unit operates at the highest level of efficiency*.

Figure 3. Job satisfaction survey results.

Figure 4. Brief T-TPQ results (items 1 through 10 of 20 items).

Figure 5. Brief T-TPQ results (items 11 to 20 of 20 items).

DISCUSSION

The aims of this QI project were to improve teamwork and communication among surgical staff members at a suburban community hospital through the implementation of TeamSTEPPS. As teamwork is strongly correlated with job satisfaction, the author sought out to examine the effect of teamwork and communication training on job satisfaction as well (Chachula et al., 2015; Kalisch et al., 2010; Miller et al., 2018). The TeamSTEPPS training produced significant improvements in the participants' perception of teamwork and communication as well as job satisfaction. In addition, the training highlighted the staff's desire for expanded opportunities in the area of growth and development within the organization.

Teamwork and Communication

The improvements in the individual Brief T-TPQ items witnessed in this QI project were different from what was previously reported in the literature (Duclos, Peix, Piriou, and Colin, 2016; Tibbs & Moss, 2014). In this project, three items increased more than 50% from baseline: (a) *Staff assist others during high workload*; (b) *My supervisor takes time to develop a plan of care*; and (c) *My supervisor considers staff input about patient care*. It is of interest that two of these items related to staff perceptions of the supervisor and the other item was related to staff support of each other. As previously mentioned, this perioperative setting recently experienced a turnover in management. This may have contributed to a "honeymoon" effect, as the staff may have favorably viewed the new manager and the staff was more supportive of one another during this transitional phase. It is also possible that the TeamSTEPPS training had a significant

influence on staff support for each other, since it brought attention to the importance of teamwork.

In contrast to what was witnessed in the project setting, Tibbs and Moss (2014) administered the T-TPQ before and after implementing TeamSTEPPS training. The two question items that demonstrated the most improvement in their QI project were *Staff members met to reevaluate goals when the situation changed* and *Staff members corrected each other's mistakes*. Duclos et al. (2016) conducted a large randomized control trial by intervening with a team-training program, similar to TeamSTEPPS, with surgical staff members in their setting. Although the intervention group demonstrated reductions in adverse events after the team training intervention, their findings were not statistically significant when compared to the control group. The researchers suggested that team-training programs might require major modifications to fit the surgical work setting (Duclos et al., 2016).

It is interesting to note that one item on the Brief T-TPQ, *Staff understands their roles and responsibilities*, demonstrated a decrease from baseline to follow-up. This decrease was small (9%) and could be a spurious result due to the small sample size. However, it is also possible that the training increased awareness of the importance of understanding roles and responsibilities, and thus, participants compared their work setting with a higher functioning work environment.

Job Satisfaction

Three items of the JSS improved markedly with time, while several items demonstrated minor changes, and three items actually regressed during the period of evaluation (one by 28%). The items that showed the greatest improvements were related

to (a) *satisfaction with teamwork* (improved by 61%, from 36.4% to 58.8%), (b) *organizational reward* (improved by 116%, from 13.6% to 29.4%), and (c) *physician respect* (improved by 85%, from 28.6% to 52.9%). The items that showed the greatest improvements also tended to have the lowest baseline agreement percentages. Thus, the percentage of improvement for these items may appear more dramatic.

The items that regressed were (a) *satisfaction with how much the manager gives consideration when asked a question about the staff member's work*, (b) *satisfaction with staff respect shown to the chief executive*, and (c) *satisfaction with opportunities for growth and development*. Interpreting these results was complicated in that some of the items with the most improvement in the Brief T-TPQ were also related to perceptions of management. The decreases from baseline in the area of job satisfaction with management were small (approximately 1% to 3%) and could simply be related to the small sample size. According to several researchers, job satisfaction determinants have varied by generation, which is important to note since the project hospital currently has employed four generations (Wilson, Squires, Widger, Cranley, & Tourangeau, 2008; Radford & Chapman, 2015).

The majority of the participants (73%) were veteran staff who had worked at the project facility for 10 or more years. The diffusion of innovations theory (DIT) explains that veteran staff members usually take the longest amount of time to adopt a change (Rogers, 2009). It is possible that greater improvements in teamwork, communication, and job satisfaction would have resulted if the author allocated more time between the baseline and post surveys.

As mentioned earlier in this paper, the DIT states that establishing “champions” was key in accelerating the rate of adoption of an innovation (Dearing, 2009). The timeline for this project did not allow for sufficient time for the identification of and adequate number of clinical champions. Despite the best efforts of the author, changes in management resulted in the loss of the primary clinical champion. The champion’s encouragement may have accelerated the adoption of TeamSTEPPS by the staff who listened to and respected her.

Evaluation of the Process of TeamSTEPPS Implementation

Overall, the participants were engaged in the role-plays and group activities throughout the training. Participants provided insight regarding the TeamSTEPPS concepts during the group discussions that contributed to the group’s overall understanding of TeamSTEPPS. The TeamSTEPPS training session occurred on the same day as the staff’s annual skills day, so some staff members were anxious to complete the class as they had a long educational day ahead of them. This may have influenced their attention to the training. Additionally, it may have been beneficial to include a member from each home department (OR, PACU, and SDS) to teach parts of the course to increase staff responsiveness to the material. However, the results of this QI project suggested a high degree of staff responsiveness to the TeamSTEPPS training as 15 of the 20 items on the follow up Brief T-TPQ scored 80% or above compared to seven of the 20 items on the baseline Brief T-TPQ.

Prior to implementing TeamSTEPPS, the author reviewed the results from the 2017 Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture (HSOPSC). This survey was repeated during the one-month follow-up JSS and TeamSTEPPS surveys. Although not part of the

official analysis of the effectiveness of the QI project, it is noteworthy to examine the trends from 2017 to 2018. The results from the 2018 HSOPSC showed a small increase in the average score for the question item *Hospital units work well together to provide the best care for patients* (3.86 in 2017 to 3.9 in 2018, 0.04 difference). However, staff reported a decrease in satisfaction with working with staff from other hospital units (3.52 in 2017 to 3.43 in 2018, -0.09 difference). Unfortunately, the data provided were aggregated and included data from all hospital units. The 2018 HSOPSC results highlighted the urgent need to implement TeamSTEPPS hospital wide, as opposed to a single service line such as surgical services, to improve teamwork throughout the project facility.

Limitations

There were several limitations to this QI project. First, the new surgical nursing director started the day before the training was provided. Several questions on both surveys pertained to the “supervisor.” Therefore, pre-training results may reflect the previous supervisor’s behavior and traits, whereas post-training results may reflect the new supervisor. Clapper and Kong (2012) argued that leadership was key to threading together the TeamSTEPPS concepts. The change in the nursing director may have also affected staff, as they had to adapt to a new leadership style while attempting to implement concepts taught in the TeamSTEPPS training session.

Another potential limitation was that AHRQ (2018) suggested performing a readiness assessment prior to implementation of TeamSTEPPS. Although the project facility’s administration thought this group was ready to be trained on TeamSTEPPS in April 2018 when this QI project was approved, it is possible that they were less receptive

to the training in September 2018. Therefore, staff readiness may have affected results of the current project, demonstrating real life barriers to implementation of QI projects.

Although the one-month response rate was relatively high (74%), various factors contributed to the attrition rate. The surgical director did not complete the post surveys because of his position as the supervisor and his job duties were not directly related to patient care. The OR's response rate was the lowest, which could be attributed to the pace of the unit (OR response rate 50% versus 100% and 100% for PACU and SDS, respectively). Staff members in the OR were less accessible as their work environment is sterile, fast-paced, and demanding as surgeries are continuous throughout the day and night. Future QI projects should consider different approaches to incentivize units with low response rates.

Lastly, the project facility also administered two other surveys hospital-wide with much larger monetary incentives, which created some competition as well as survey burden on the staff members. The staff members could have also experienced survey fatigue and response bias. Some survey takers marked the same answer option for each question on the follow-up surveys, which suggested the validity may be compromised. It is possible that they wanted to complete the surveys quickly without taking the proper amount of time to read, reflect, and accurately answer the questions. Response bias refers to the survey takers' tendency to report a certain answer, such as always agreeing, regardless of the question content (Polit & Beck, 2017). Although the QI project team ensured confidentiality of the survey responses, some staff members may have still feared retaliation if their supervisor saw their responses.

Clinical Implications

It is essential to explore why the participants grew increasingly dissatisfied with opportunities for growth and development within the organization one month after the TeamSTEPPS training class. The item from the JSS that demonstrated a large decrement (-28% from baseline) warrants attention from hospital administrators and clinical directors. A possible contributory factor may have been the lack of education classes for the two years prior to the TeamSTEPPS training course. The training course may have reminded the staff of how important it is that institutions foster the growth and development of their healthcare providers. As there has been a strong association between opportunities for growth and development and job satisfaction, dissatisfaction with growth and development may lead to employee turnover and compromise patient safety (Miller et al., 2018).

It is vital to provide team-building sessions to improve teamwork and patient safety. Furthermore, teamwork has been associated with high morale and job satisfaction, which has served as a burnout antagonist (Chachula et al., 2015; Miller et al., 2018). TeamSTEPPS is an evidence-based training program designed to improve teamwork, but the classes may be resource intensive. Furthermore, cultural and generational differences, which may contribute to differences in communication and perceptions of job satisfaction, have not been specifically addressed in the TeamSTEPPS curriculum. Future teamwork classes may wish to include content related to culture and age to improve healthcare team performance.

The results from this project provided baseline data than can be used in future benchmarking for quality improvement. Benchmarking is defined as evaluating

something by comparing it to a certain standard (Dale, Bamford, & Wiele, 2016). The author has planned to present the results to both the hospital administration as well as the surgical staff. Both groups will be encouraged to reflect on the meaningful aspects and results of the project and queried as to how they would like to see this work move forward. Additionally, clinical champions will be sought to continue implementation of TeamSTEPPS concepts and motivate frontline staff.

CONCLUSION

The aims of this QI project were to improve teamwork and communication among surgical staff through the implementation of TeamSTEPPS at the project facility. Furthermore, the author sought to improve job satisfaction as a secondary result of improving teamwork and communication. The significant improvements in the JSS and Brief T-TPQ scores suggested that implementing TeamSTEPPS training had a positive impact on perceptions of teamwork and communication from the surgical staff at the project facility. However, the TeamSTEPPS training had a greater influence on teamwork and communication than on job satisfaction, suggesting that administrators should address the multiple factors that affect job satisfaction simultaneously. This QI project has added to the literature by confirming the results found by other researchers as well as has provided testimony to the implementation process associated with TeamSTEPPS in community-based, acute settings. Further research should focus on patient outcomes as they relate to TeamSTEPPS implementation.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 2

Table of Evidence for Implementation and Evaluation of TeamSTEPPS®

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To implement and eval compliance with SBAR during COS report (Achrekar et al., 2016)	Pre-Posttest design IDV: Educational intervention "SIM" DV: SBAR competency	Simple random sampling n = 20 Bedside nurses (RN/LVN) setting unknown	Author created nurses' SBAR opinion scale: 7 questions Likert scale. Reliability statistics not provided Checklist for audit inter-reliability 29 items dichotomous S-10, B-7, A-7, R-5, (k=0.91, P<0.001).	N=20 1 st audit, N=19 2 nd audit, N=17 for nurse opinion survey. Stat significant correlation b/t audit score and higher education level (grad RNs) (P=0.019). Significant improv. b/t two rounds of audits (P=0.043) and "situation" part of SBAR (P = 0.043). Only 70% documented plan of care. Almost 80% find SBAR helpful, 63% feel that SBAR improves patient safety, and 47% said recommendation was hard	Small sample size so not generalizable, also in India. Important to include pt because allows them to ask questions, clarify, and provide more info, calms the pt, makes them more compliant and increases satisfaction
To determine factors that inhibit speaking up, perceived usefulness of communication training, and increase self-efficacy & communication of pt safety concerns	Phase 1: Qualitative with focus groups Phase 2: pre/post-test QI- implementing team communication training adapted from TeamSTEPPS	Purposive sampling Phase 1: n = 34 Phase 2: n = 42 Surgical oncology staff from thoracic and urology services	Phase 1: Interviews Phase 2: 1) Post-training eval (Previously established in other comm. training studies) Likert scale, also watched videos to id behaviors, interrater	Focus group themes: staff rapport & personality, perceived competence & efficacy of speaking up, role relations & hierarchy, fear of retaliation, institutional regulations, & time pressure Self-efficacy in communicating pt safety concerns higher after training (mean from 4.02 to 4.32; t ₄₀ = 2.76, p =0 .009, d=0.48)	Participants agreed that training will help their practice and promote pt safety, found instructional methods helpful (roleplaying, lecture, case videos). Participants likely to stop to ask for clarity but less

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
(D'agostino et al., 2017)			reliability 80% for process tasks and 76.7% for comm skills. 2) Pre/post test		likely to minimize the hierarchy. Limit = no baseline data, next time can give a pt scenario beforehand, response bias
To improve staff perception of communication and teamwork by implementing TeamSTEPPS (Gaston, Short, Ralyea, & Casterline, 2016)	Mixed methods: Pre/Post-test design and focus groups IDV: TeamSTEPPS training DV: perception of teamwork/comm, knowledge, # of incident reports	Convenience sampling n = 110 (RNs, CNAs, & MDs) n = 44/110 for focus groups Large academic hospital, 3 oncology units	T-TPQ Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture TeamSTEPPS Learning Benchmark Test Patient Incident Reports	T-TPQ mean at one month after training 4.58 ($t_{180} = -6.22, p = .000$) HSOPSC 17% increase in teamwork within units, 21% increase in comm openness ($p < .05$) LBT increased by 2%, not significant ($p = .207$) Incident reports remained the same Common themes: TeamSTEPPS most useful for huddle, CUS tool helpful for clarifying, TeamSTEPPS can be reinforced by adding it to hospital orientation and posters	Limit: incident reports are self-reported, unless caught by another staff, some staff already had comm and teamwork training, no control group Incident reporting system should have place to indicate incident r/t teamwork or comm issue
To determine the effectiveness of teamwork reinforcement interventions on sustained teamwork behaviors (Lee et al., 2017)	Prospective pre-post cohort study IV: 4 reinforcement activities 1) lecture with videos on leadership for nurses, 2) online self-paced module on comm, 3) emailed 1 page	Convenience sampling n = 50 interdisciplinary members (Surgeons, PAs, NP, CRNAs, anesthesiologists, nurses) Orthopedic sx unit	OTAS by 2 observers before and after – reliable and valid for general, urology, & vasc sx, interrater validity by reaching consensus	Leadership ($p = 0.022$) and communication ($p = 0.044$) behaviors improved after reinforcement techniques for all staff Just nursing $P = 0.016$ for leadership and $P = 0.028$ for communication Anesthesia did not improve in either	Level III evidence Greatest improvement in leadership arena Limit = single site, academic, limits generalizability to sites with less org support; also some new hires didn't get the TeamSTEPPS training

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	summary on leadership skills, & 4) 1 hr period grand rounds DV: sustained teamwork behavior				
To examine the knowledge, attitude, and performance of ED staff following TeamSTEPPS training (Lisbon et al., 2016)	QI, Pilot study IV: TeamSTEPPS training DV: patient safety knowledge, attitude, and behavior of staff	Convenience sampling n = 113 Multidisc team (MDs, residents, nursing & ancillary staff) from academic hospital's ED	TeamSTEPPS Knowledge Test and AHRQ Hospital Survey attitude at 0, 45, 90 days after training Obs tool to evaluate behavior during and freq of huddles (non-validated), assessed by 1 st yr med students "secret shoppers"	Patient safety knowledge improved after 45 days from the training (χ^2 , $P < .05$) but decreased by 2 questions by day 90 Communication attitudes increased according to AHRQ survey ($P < .05$) and sustained over 90 days Speaking freely and discussing errors Huddles observed 64% of the time and 47% reported using CUS	Also had champions Taught by IP education team Limits = No control group Clinical outcomes not studied
To examine the implementation of shift-change handoff communication as part of TeamSTEPPS (Natafqi et al., 2017)	Qualitative How implementation attributes correspond with shift change handoff performance	Convenience sampling n = 8 critical access hospitals, med-surg units	Semi-structured interviews with key informants (questions were provided) TENTS tool for observations of shift-change handoff process – 5 aspects of teamwork, score of 0-3 for each, total 15 for each hospital	4 themes (purpose, facilitators, barriers, & trajectory of handoff implementation) compared b/t high and low performing hospitals: 1) Bottom-up concerns about efficiency (i.e., Discussing issues irrelevant to patient care during handoff), top-down concerns about staff performance, & goal of pt & family involvement 2) Local & institutional (i.e., aligning with org's values & culture), champion and team (leadership rounding & sharing int & ext success stories), patient,	Standardized procedures allowed minimization of info lost during hand off Leadership support may be more important at smaller hospitals where leaders are closer to front line nurses because their findings are slightly diff than the lit Good catch program: Rewarding RNs for catching near-misses

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				<p>& technical factors (i.e., pocket cards, badge buddies, checklists, pt comm boards, emails weekly)</p> <p>3) Punitive culture for checklists; low leadership support for time and money, no official method for receiving feedback, resistance to change by veteran nursing staff</p> <p>High performing focused more on support from leadership, getting buy in, & being more transparent and aware of barriers from beginning, both had resistance and lack of MD support</p>	
To examine the role of TBL in team skills, clinical/professional behaviors, & learning style (Oldland, Currey, Considine, & Allen, 2017)	<p>Qualitative, Exploratory descriptive</p> <p>If and how TBL affected teamwork skills, learning styles, prof behavior during class and clinicals</p>	<p>Purposive sampling</p> <p>n = 159</p> <p>postgrad (MSN) critical, intensive, emergency, & cardiac care students</p> <p>Australia</p>	N/A to qualitative studies	<p>3 themes:</p> <p>1) Deep learning, improved communication because nurses had to speak concisely or be challenged by others; revealed personality traits such as domineering by speaking over others</p> <p>2) Confidence in prob solving, knowledge, reasons to decisions in practice, ex: speaking up to senior staff to advocate for pt & active member of interdisc. team,</p> <p>3) Clinical and Prof Behavior such as leadership skills, improvements in colleague and patient collabs through multidisc comm skills, patient advocacy, peer mentorship; ex: listening skills and negotiating to resolve conflicts, combat poor practice, id strengths/ weaknesses</p>	<p>Academic instead of clinical setting but students already RNs; learn by approaching situations individually and then as a team;</p> <p>Peer eval important to reinforce good behavior and fix bad ones.</p> <p>Limit = Reflection was worth part of grade and participants may want to please instructors</p>

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To evaluate TeamSTEPPS training in an inpatient environment (Vertino, 2014)	Pre-exp pretest/posttest repeated-measures IDV: TeamSTEPPS training DV: Leadership, mutual support, team structure, communication & situation monitoring Covariates: Demographics	Convenience sampling n=18 Nursing staff (RNs, LPNs, NAs) on hospital unit, location unreported	T-TAQ (30 Likert scale items, Cronbach's .70-.83) 2 extra questions added to posttest about perceived benefit of TeamSTEPPS on culture and teamwork	38.4% BSN and 30.8% ADN Total T-TAQ significantly increased ($p \leq .001$), stat significance ($p \leq .001$) for all 5 teamwork constructs. No stat significance b/t occupation or yrs of exp in TTAQ scores. 82% felt TeamSTEPPS improved teamwork, ($\chi^2 = 7.118, p = 0.008$).	Authors reported right-skewed data, above high agreement with survey questions so they used the 'reflect-and-log procedure' to decrease affect. Coaching and mentoring offered afterwards for sustenance. Limitations: small sample, mandatory training by admin so created bias, fatigue from attending training after work
To assess a community hospital's compliance with recommended TeamSTEPPS best practices from Weaver et al. (Ward, Zhu, Lampman, & Stewart, 2015)	Qualitative Implementation approaches by community hospital staff and how they compare with best practices from Weaver et al.	Snowball sampling n=57 people from 22 hospitals (32 MTTs, 16 implementation team members, and 9 unit staff) Community hospitals in Iowa	Semi-structured interviews, 11 key questions from Weaver et al.	1) Each sent an avg of 4 people to MTT session 2) Training site staff adhered to set curriculum 3) Training group size varied 20-40 people 4) 33% used low fidelity sim like role playing 5) Only 2 hospitals (13%) were providing feedback during training sessions Evaluation right after training, later HSOPSC to examine staff perception and monthly incident reports of patient safety events	3 areas to improve for implementation: 1) Sending MDs to MTT 2) Active learning approaches 3) Develop action plan for follow up with staff Many other articles on TeamSTEPPS are at large academic medical centers Small community hospitals have less resources – personnel and money
To examine relationship between teamwork and clinician	Systematic review	n = 25 studies	12 studies (48%) used NWI to operationalize teamwork	Staff that perceive higher levels of teamwork also reported higher occupational well-being or less job	Poor team behaviors: actions aren't coordinated well, goals aren't communicated, and staff

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
occupational well-being (Welp & Manser, 2016)		24 cross sectional self-report, 1 pre and post shift diary 19 studies (76%) surveyed only nurses	11 studies (44%) used MBI or short version of	strain; Effect size small to moderate ($\beta = -12.85, f^2 = 0.13, r = -0.47$)	input is not invited by fellow team members → decreases ability to provide safe care Ineffective teamwork can lead to higher workload for individuals and decreased employee well being Benefits of effective teamwork: balances work loads, helps prevent errors, & provides social/emo support in demanding work conditions
To improve staff attitude about teamwork and communication after implementing an interprofessional education course (Wong, Gang, Szyld & Mahoney, 2016)	Mixed methods: 1) Qual Focus groups for needs assessment and learning obj for course 2) Pre-post observational/interventional IV: Interprofessional education course (Adapted TeamSTEPPS) DV: Staff attitudes about teamwork and interprofessional communication	Convenience sampling n=20 for 3 focus groups n=72 staff for 12 TeamSTEPPS sessions, ER nurses and residents at large academic hospital	T-TAQ before and right after HSOPSC before and one year post intervention	Stat significant improvements in team structure, situational monitoring, mutual support, & leadership ($P < 0.0001, P = 0.014, P = 0.003, \& P = 0.029$) on T-TAQ Stat significant improvements in 3 out of 6 questions directly r/t teamwork and communication on HSOPSC: freq of error/near miss reporting ($P = 0.028$), teamwork in hospital units ($P = 0.035$), & handoff and transition of care reports ($P = 0.024$)	Other 3 HSOPSC constructs, teamwork across hospital units, comm openness, & feedback and com, about error still showed improvements; comm on T-TAQ as well, even though not stat significant Other probs revealed: probs with staffing → needs for systems support Limit = natural disaster and hospital closed down after intervention, not able to get attending MD to come to training, response bias on surveys

Note. Admin = Administration, ADN = Associate Degree Nurse, B/t = Between, Comm. = Communication, COS = Change of shift, Collabs = Collaboration(s), CNA = Certified Nursing Assistant, Diff = Different/Difference, Eval = Evaluate, Exp = Experience, HCAHPS = Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Provider and Systems, Id = Identify, Improv = Improvements, Interdisc = Interdisciplinary, LPN = Licensed Practical Nurse, MD = Medical Doctor, MSN = Masters of Science in Nursing, Multidisc = Multidisciplinary, NA = Nurse Aid/Assistant, Obs = Observation(al) Prob = Problem, Prof = Professional, Pt = Patient, QI = Quality Improvement, RN = Registered Nurse, SBAR = Situation, Background, Assessment, Recommendation, SIM = Self-instructed module, Stat = Statistic(ally), TBL = Team-Based Learning, TeamSTEPPS = Team Strategies and Tools to Enhance Performance and Patient Safety, T-TAQ = TeamSTEPPS Teamwork Attitude Questionnaire, T-TPQ = TeamSTEPPS Teamwork Perceptions Questionnaire , Wk = Week(s), Yrs = Years

APPENDIX B

BRIEF TEAMSTEPPS TEAMWORK PERCEPTION QUESTIONNAIRE (T-TPQ)

Adapted by Dr. Jessica Castner from AHRQ; Survey #1: Pre/Post for participants

1. **My supervisor/manager provides opportunities to discuss the unit's performance after an event**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
2. **My supervisor/manager takes time to meet with staff to develop a plan for care**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
3. **My supervisor/manager considers staff input when making decisions about patient care**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
4. **My supervisor/manager models appropriate team behavior**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
5. **Information regarding patient care is explained to patients and their families in lay terms**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
6. **When communicating with patients, staff allow enough time for questions**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
7. **Staff relay relevant information in a timely manner**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
8. **Staff verbally verify information they receive from one another**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
9. **Staff assist fellow staff during high workload**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
10. **Staff caution each other about potentially dangerous situations**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
11. **Staff advocate for patients even when their opinion conflicts with that of a senior member of the unit**
 N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

12. Feedback between staff is delivered in a way that promotes positive interactions and future change

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

13. Staff exchange relevant information as it becomes available

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

14. Staff continuously scan the environment for important information

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

15. Staff meets to reevaluate patient care goals when aspects of the situation have changed

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

16. Staff share information regarding potential complications (e.g., patient changes, bed availability)

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

17. My unit has clearly articulated goals

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

18. My unit operates at a high level of efficiency

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

19. Staff understand their roles and responsibilities

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

20. Staff within my unit share information that enables timely decision making by the direct patient care team

N/A Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

APPENDIX C

HEALTHCARE ENVIRONMENT SURVEY JOB SATISFACTION SUBSCALE
(JSS)

By Dr. John Nelson; Survey #2: Pre/Post for participants

1. I am satisfied with how well nurses and staff in my unit/department work together as a team.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

2. I am satisfied with how the organization rewards me when I consider the amount of effort I put forth.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

3. I am satisfied in my daily work how I am able to build trust with the patient and family by utilizing effective communication.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

4. I am satisfied with how physicians I work with are respectful of the skill and knowledge of all the staff in my unit/department

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

5. I am satisfied with how the manager of my unit/department gives me adequate and meaningful consideration when I ask him or her a question about my work.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

6. I am satisfied with the level of respect staff within my profession show to the chief executive of my profession (e.g. the Chief Medical Officer is well respected by physicians, or the Chief Nurse Officer is well respected by nurses, etc.).

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

7. I am satisfied with my opportunities for growth and development within this organization.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

8. I am satisfied with the amount of time I have to complete the tasks required of me.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

9. I am satisfied with how much control I have over my own work. My supervisors do not make all the decisions for me.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

10. I am satisfied with the input I have into my final schedule prior to the roster being posted.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

11. I am satisfied with the availability of equipment needed to do my job.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree			Neutral	Strongly Agree		

APPENDIX D
JOB SATISFACTION SURVEY RESULTS

Table 3

Job Satisfaction Survey Results

Question	% Strongly Agree/Agree Pre N = 22	% Strongly Agree/Agree Post N = 17	% of improvement	% of drop
Satisfaction with organizational reward	13.6%	29.4%	116%	
Satisfaction with time to complete tasks	27.3%	29.4%	7.7%	
Satisfaction with physicians respectfulness	28.6%	52.9%	85%	
Satisfaction with staff respect to chief executive	31.8%	29.4%		-7.5%
Satisfaction with available equipment	36.4%	41.2%	13.2%	
Satisfaction with control over own work	36.4%	47.1%	29.4%	
Satisfaction with teamwork on unit	36.4%	58.8%	61.5%	
Satisfaction with growth & development opportunities	40.9%	29.4%		-28.1%
Satisfaction with input into final schedule	40.9%	41.2%	0.7%	
Satisfaction with manager consideration when I have questions	54.5%	52.9%		-2.9%
Satisfaction with ability to build trust with patients and families utilizing effective communication	66.7%	70.6%	5.8%	

APPENDIX E
BRIEF T-TPQ RESULTS

Table 4

Brief Team STEPPS Teamwork Perceptions Questionnaire (T-TPQ) Results

Question	% Strongly Agree/Agree Pre N = 22	% Strongly Agree/Agree Post N = 17	% of improvement	% of drop
Supervisor considers staff input about patient care	40.9%	62.5%	52.8%	
Supervisor consults staff to develop plan for care	45.5%	68.8%	51.2%	
Supervisor models team behavior	50%	70.6%	41.2%	
Supervisor discusses unit's performance after an event	54.5%	73.3%	34.5%	
Staff assist fellow staff	59.1%	94.1%	59.2%	
Unit has clearly articulated goals	61.9%	82.4	33.1%	
Staff advocate for patients	65%	87.5%	34.6%	
Feedback is delivered positively	70%	76.5%	9.3%	
Staff exchange relevant information when available	71.4%	80%	12%	
Staff scan environment for important information	71.4%	82.4%	15.4%	
Staff reevaluate patient care goals when situations change	71.4%	87.5%	22.5%	
Staff share information to enable timely decision making	75%	82.4%	9.9%	
Staff caution each other	77.3%	88.2%	14.1%	
Staff relay relevant information timely	81%	100%	23.5%	
Staff share information regarding potential complications	85%	93.3%	9.8%	
Staff allow enough time for questions when communicating with patients	85.7%	94.1%	9.8%	
Staff verbally verify information they receive	86.4%	88.2%	2%	
Staff understand their roles and responsibilities	90.5%	82.4%		-8.9%
Unit operates at a high level of efficiency	90.5%	94.1%	4.0%	
Information is explained to patients and families in lay terms	90.5%	100%	10.5%	